

Madani: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin
Volume 1, Nomor 10, November 2023, Halaman 294-300
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E-ISSN: [2986-6340](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10115384)
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10115384>

Strategy of School Principal Increases Quality of Education in Facing Asean Economic Communities (MEA) at SMK N 1 Bukittinggi

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Abstract

In this article, the researcher try see the phenomena about ASEAN Economic Community. Indonseia is kind of ASEAN Economic Communtiy must prepare quality of human resources to face ASEAN Economic Communtiy. The education is way to progress quality of human resources. SMK N 1 Bukiittinggi is a education institution that express alumnus to word indurtry. In this research we going to role of head master of SMK 1 Bukittinggi to make quality of eduction to face ASEAN Economic Communtiy. I this research, researcher use qualitative method with phenomenology model. To get data, the researcher use interview and document study. Finding of research, to progress quality of education, the head master progress competence of teacher, student, development of curriculum and infrasrcture

Keywords: *↯ role, head master, quality education, ASEAN Economic Community*

Article Info

Received date: 25 October 2023

Revised date: 30 October, 2023

Accepted date: 09 November 2023

INTRODUCTION

Since the enactment of the ASEAN Economic Community (MEA) in 2015 which aims to create ASEAN as a single market and unified production base. There will be free flow of goods, services, factors of production, investment and capital, and the elimination of tariffs for trade between ASEN countries. (Suara Karya: 2015). The enactment of the MEA makes countries race to build production that can compete in the ASEAN market. Every production produced later is expected to be able to compete in the ASEAN market. With the enactment of the MEA since 2015, the ASEAN countries, this also applies to Indonesia as one of the ASEAN countries.

Improvement in the fields of production, must be accompanied by quality resources. Zainun (2001: 6) states that quality human resources in the real sense are the work done to produce something that is desired. Quality resources are expected to produce products that are able to compete in the ASEAN market. In order to compete in the ASEAN market, Indonesia as one of the ASEAN countries is faced with the challenge of improving the quality of human resources. Improving the quality of Indonesian human resources as an effort to build productivity in the face of competition from ASEAN countries.

One of the most important efforts in efforts to improve the quality of human resources is through the education sector. Education as a conscious effort to build quality, quality human resources so that they can compete and compete. This is in line with Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System which states that education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills needed by him, society, nation and state. From the law on National Education System, several indicators of the quality of education in Indonesia

can be seen, namely the development of self-potential, religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skill.

Thus, efforts to increase human resources are efforts that are integrated with improving the quality of education. Education as a very vital sector in the framework of building quality human resources, requires enormous attention from all parties, because it involves the quality and quality of the nation, especially with the existence of competition when the MEA begins. Widodo (2015: 296) stated that to hack HR problems in Indonesia, education is the most decisive thing. With the implementation of education in Indonesia as a whole, it will be able to produce potential generations who are ready to compete on the world market. This is what is being sought by educational institutions in Indonesia. An educational institution is an institution or place where the educational process takes place with the aim of changing individual behavior in a better direction through interaction with the surrounding environment (Fiandi & Ilmi, 2022). All educational institutions in Indonesia have the duties and responsibilities in order to build a potential generation and be able to compete in the world market.

One of the educational institutions that is currently trying to give birth to potential generations who are ready to compete is the Vocational High School (SMK). Vocational schools, which are educational institutions that are based on skills and expertise, strive to produce talented and potential workers so they can compete. Vocational schools which are educational institutions that produce skilled workers are ready to jump into the business world. With the enactment of the MEA, SMK seeks to produce skilled workers who are ready to compete in the ASEAN Economic Community (MEA).

However, all forms of vocational programs and activities in giving birth to skilled workers require a strategy and role of the principal as the leader. The principal as the leader has authority and policy in an effort to improve the quality of education. The role of the principal is very decisive in achieving the expected educational goals. Therefore, in this study, researchers will look at the strategy of the head of the SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi in improving the quality of education to face the ASEAN Economic Community (MEA).

THEORITICAL REVIEW

Principal

Education is the main determinant of a nation's civilization. The progress and retreat of a nation can be seen from the quality of human resources in the country. the main factor to be able to realize quality resources is through education. With the meaning of the word that the progress of a nation is determined by the education carried out in the country. For that, an education plan and plan is needed to answer quality human resource needs.

In order to produce quality education as a generation of the nation, professional management is needed. To be able to create professional management, professional figures and figures are certainly needed. Professional figures or figures of education cannot be separated from the roles and responsibilities of the principal. The principal is the most important component that has a role in creating quality education. Rosyadi, Prajono (2015: 125) states that the role of principal is very influential on the growth and development of education in improving human resources.

Rohiat (2008: 14) suggests that the principal as manager and executive in the school shows that he is a managerial technical executor and has skills in running the school. The skills of these principals will later be able to build schools that give birth to human resources that are able to compete and compete. Mulyasa (2004: 25) also explains that principals have responsibility for the administration of education, school administration, fostering education staff and utilization and maintenance of facilities and infrastructure. Then, the principal needs to have a strategy in empowering educators and education through cooperation, providing

opportunities to improve professionalism, and encouraging the involvement of all educators and education staff to participate in supporting school programs (Mulyasa, 2009: 103). All these things in order to realize quality education. With the meaning of the word that the principal is a component that plays a role in building quality education in order to produce quality human resources.

Quality of Education

Quality or quality is a planned hope in the world of education. To create a quality educational institution, quality standards are needed. Quality standards are a set of benchmarks for the performance of an education system which includes input, process, results, output and benefits of education must be fulfilled by work units in an educational institution (Fiandi & Sesmiarni, 2023). The quality of education requires a well-planned plan and great responsibility. Rohiat (2010: 52) states that quality or quality is a picture and overall characteristics of goods or services that show the ability to satisfy the expected needs. In the world of quality education includes input, process, and educational output. Besides that, in the context of education, education products are services and services. These quality services and services will later determine the quality of the human resources of a nation. Sudradjad (2005: 17) suggests that quality education is education that produces graduates who have competencies, both academic and vocational, based on social and personal competencies, and noble moral values, which are all forms of life skills.

Besides that, quality education is an education that produces graduates who are competent who have the power to compete in a healthy manner. Sukmadinata et al. (2010: 5) stated that the quality of education is of the utmost importance. To implement a quality program several strong bases are needed, namely: 1) commitment to change; 2) clear understanding of existing conditions; 3) have a clear vision of the future; 4) have a clear plan. With this, it is expected to produce a quality painting.

Graduates who are passionate, not only have the ability, but are able to maximize this ability to compete with others. That is, quality is not only in theory, but this also applies in practice. The quality and quality of the graduation can be seen how much benefits can be given, both directly and indirectly the benefits of the lives of many people. especially in the world of global competition today. The quality and quality of human resources will have a huge impact on the civilization of a nation. On the other hand, education that is meaningful cannot only be seen from the quality of graduates, but also covers how education is able to meet customer needs in accordance with applicable quality standards (Mulyasa: 2009: 226).

ASEAN Economic Community (MEA)

At the moment, the issue of MEA is being discussed. Syukriah and Hamdani (2013: 112) suggest that the MEA is an ASEAN community in the economic field (ASEAN Economic Community) designed at the 9th ASEAN Summit in Bali in 2003 known as the Bali Concord II. According to Widodo (2015: 299) MEA is a form of world market in Asia. With the existence of ME A there is trade and investment freely signaling the existence of obstacles geographically. According to Tyas and Safitri (2014: 43) that MEA manifests the desire of ASEAN countries to realize ASEAN into a solid economic region, by realizing 4 pillars namely 1) single market and production base, 2) high competitive economic zone, 3) regions with equal economic development and 4) areas that are fully integrated with the global economy.

With the word meaning, MEA is an economic forum for ASEN countries in order to create global economic competition. The existence of the MEA gives freedom for every country to build economy and invest in other countries. Freedom that requires every country to produce products that have competitiveness with other countries. The MEA opens up a challenge as well as an opportunity for a country to prove that the country is able to become a country that competes with other countries. With the existence of MEA, geographical

boundaries are no longer a problem that must be faced. MEA breaks down the geographical wall, and opens up huge opportunities to become a strong and strong country in the economic sector.

METHOD

This type of research is descriptive qualitative research that departs from a phenomenological view, where in this paper the researcher tries to see the steps and efforts made in dealing with an event that is happening. Ahimsa (2012: 273) argues that phenomenology can be interpreted as "the knowledge of what someone sees, what he feels and knows in his immediate awareness and experience. This research is intended to reveal things that are done by an educational institution in an effort to deal with the phenomenon that occurs.

The research is focused on a secondary education institution namely Vocational High School (SMK) in the city of Bukittinggi. In this study, the author tries to reveal the role of the Principal as the leader of this educational institution. Therefore, to obtain data and information, the researcher conducted an interview directly with the resource person, namely the Principal of Bukittinggi State Vocational High School 1. Besides that, to strengthen data and information through wawacanra, researchers also presented data from documents that the researchers got from the official website of SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Since the adoption of the ASEAN Economic Community (MEA) in 2015, competition in the economic sector has increased. Each country is given the freedom to market products to other countries without being limited by geographical space. Every country strives to produce quality products. This has become a challenge for the country of Indonesia, as one of the ASEAN countries. Indonesia is expected to be able to compete in this MEA by producing quality products. To get a quality product, quality resources are needed too, and to get quality resources, education is the key.

The world of education in Indonesia today has a very heavy duty in efforts to produce quality human resources. One of the efforts made to produce skilled and quality resources is through vocational education institutions. Vocational High School is one of the educational institutions that is ready to create skilled workers in the industrial field. According to Murniati (2009: 127) that vocational education has a very strategic role in national development efforts, especially in the social and economic sectors. Vocational education is an investment to produce skilled Indonesian people. Bukittinggi State Vocational School 1 is a vocational high school that prepares graduates to become skilled labor in the industrial world. This can be seen from the data obtained through documents on the official website of SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi, where Vocational Schools prepare their graduates with skills and competencies that are divided into departments - majors needed in the field.

Teacher Competence

As one of the educational institutions that are expected to be able to give birth to graduates who are ready to face the MEA, especially in the field of industry, SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi undertakes various efforts and efforts to improve the quality of graduates. Mr. Yon Afrizal, S, Pd, as the headmaster, has a very big role in efforts to improve the quality of education at SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi. From the results of interviews with the Principal, the programs carried out in the rangkan to improve the quality of education to face the MEA are by increasing teacher competencies and qualifications. Where there are some teachers who are given the opportunity to improve their academic qualifications from S 1 to level S 2. The improvement of academic qualifications aims to improve teacher competency and ability,

which in turn is expected to have a profound influence on the quality of education in SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi.

Then, in addition to developing academic qualifications, the teachers at SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi also get education and training. There was even one of the teachers of SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi who got a certificate from Astra Honda, where with the existence of the certificate, the teacher concerned could determine whether Bukittinggi SMK N 1 students were eligible to work in Astra Honda workshops. Rohiat (2010: 27) explains that the management of teaching staff is the responsibility of the principal. The principal is required to take responsibility for the success or failure of members. The ability of the principal includes 1) obtaining competent members, 2) forming members to adjust to their duties, 3) empowering members effectively and 4) giving opportunities to members to develop themselves continuously. According to Sari (2013: 94) that being a professional educator will not just be realized without the motivation to develop themselves, achieve, enrich knowledge, learn what is not understood and try to advance the quality of education. With the meaning of the word that one of the strategies that needs to be done by principals in improving the quality of education to face the MEA is to develop the qualifications and competencies of educators.

Student Competence

Then, in addition to increasing teacher competence through developing academic qualifications, the activities held by the Bukittinggi State Vocational High School 1 principal in improving the quality of education are collaborating with outside parties. From the data obtained through interviews with the head of Bukittinggi State Vocational School 1, information was obtained that SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi cooperated with Astra Honda. Where in the motorcycle engineering department, the Bukittinggi 1 State Vocational School cooperates with Astra Honda. Where Bukittinggi State Vocational School 1 has been trusted to be a place of competency testing. Besides that, in the engineering department of the road vehicle, SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi received guidance from Auto 2000, with the provision of one unit of Avanza in 2005 as a place for student practice activities. In the mapping survey technique, Bukittinggi Vocational High School 1 also cooperates with the Indonesian Survey Association. For the development of students' abilities, the Bukittinggi Vocational High School 1 also held Industrial Work Practices (Prakerin / PKL), where students study directly in the field for 3 months in a predetermined industry. Besides that, the Bukittinggi State Vocational High School 1 also establishes cooperative relations with neighboring nagar such as Malaysia, Thailand and China. This shows that one of the strategies carried out by principals in improving the quality of education is by building partnerships with other parties.

According to Minister of National Education Regulation No. 19 of 2007 concerning Education Management Standards states that each school establishes partnerships with other relevant institutions, relating to input, process, output, and utilization of graduates. Strategies for building cooperation are known as cooperative strategies. According to Assauri (2013: 179) that cooperative strategy is a strategy where an organization works with one or several organizations, other institutions to achieve mutually agreed objectives. With the cooperation carried out by SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi, all forms of shortcomings experienced during the education process can be covered up.

To determine the quality of students starting from the time of recruitment. Through interviews with the Principal, it is said that in the process of recruiting students, there are several criteria that must be met, including not color blindness, minimum height of 160 for mechanical engineering and geomatics. But one thing that is very interesting is that SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi will receive directly without a test of prospective students who have the Qur'an and MTQ champions. This was done because the SMK Negeri 1 concluded that prospective students who had the Qur'an and MTQ champions were students who had good

attitudes, and had good abilities. This has become quite special in the recruitment process at SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi. Furthermore, in an effort to develop the ability of students, SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi, besides sending students to study in the industry through the activities of street vendors, self-development is also carried out through extracurricular activities. Extracurricular activities are carried out to channel the potential and interests possessed by students.

Education curriculum

Regarding the curriculum applied at SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi, from the data obtained through interviews with principals it was stated that SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi used the national curriculum as a compulsory curriculum. However, to develop the quality of education, SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi also developed the curriculum needed by the industry. The Principal stated that when visiting the Korean region, the Koreana party offered to the Bukittinggi 1 State Vocational School to make Samsung products. That is, in conducting curriculum development, beside the national curriculum, the State Vocational School 1 tries to adjust to the needs of the industry today. The State Vocational High School 1 tries to provide basic concepts to students, then students are asked to develop them in the industrial world through PKL activities. Rohiat (2010: 21) explains that students conduct learning activities based on the curriculum that apply and are always adapted to the development of science and technology. The curriculum formulated must be in accordance with the philosophy and ideals of the nation, the development of students, and the progress of society.

Facilities and infrastructure

One of the factors that determine the quality and quality of students is the existence of facilities and infrastructure. From the data obtained through interviews with the Principal where it was explained that the facilities and infrastructure in SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi were the most complete facilities and infrastructure. But to improve the quality of education, the Bukittinggi State Vocational School 1 collaborates with the industry, this is done if the needs of facilities and infrastructure in Bukittinggi N 1 Vocational School have not been optimally fulfilled. The students are programmed to follow industrial work practices, which through this activity is a solution if the infrastructure in Bukittinggi 1 Public Vocational School is inadequate. With this activity, students are expected to be able to develop the skills they have gained in school.

Rohiat (2010: 26) states that educational facilities and infrastructure are all movable and immovable objects needed to support learning activities, either directly or indirectly. Mulyasa (2009: 21) suggests that the management of facilities in the form of facilities and infrastructure, including procurement, maintenance, repair and development is a school policy. This delegation is done because the school knows more about the facilities needed in the education process. With the meaning of the word that the need for educational facilities and infrastructure is the responsibility of the principal. One of the things that is done by the principal in the framework of meeting the needs of these facilities and infrastructure is by establishing cooperative relations with the industrial world.

CONCLUSION

The ASEAN Economic Community is a condition that is both a challenge and an opportunity for Indonesia to prove that Indonesia can compete with other ASEAN countries. This MEA Defender demands the Indonesian state to be able to produce quality products, both products in the form of goods or services. To be able to compete in the international arena, Indonesia needs to design a strategic plan early on, and prepare quality and quality human resources. This shows that MEA is a situation that builds a paradigm of thinking for this nation to face global competition. In an effort to improve the quality and quality of Indonesian human resources, quality education is needed, because to build human resources

and the paradigm of the world, it cannot be separated from science as the fruit of education. Education is the main way to improve the quality and quality of human resources. Education holds a considerable portion of the goals of a country.

To deal with this MEA, every educational institution has the duty and responsibility to produce skilled and qualified graduates. Graduates who will later be resources that are ready to compete in the international market. Therefore, various educational activities and programs are needed to build and develop student competencies. This is the duty and responsibility of the principal as the head of an educational institution, including in vocational education institutions. Vocational schools, which are educational institutions that produce graduates who are skilled and ready to face the industrial world, need a variety of admiration and education quality improvement programs. Therefore, the headmaster of course must take a policy and attitude in an effort to increase the number of graduates of SMK Negeri 1 Bukittinggi, who will later enter the competition in the industrial world. The various steps of the strategy must be carried out by the principal, starting from improving teacher competence, student competence, curriculum development and meeting the needs of educational facilities and infrastructure. All this is done in order to produce quality graduates who will be ready to compete in the ASEAN Economic Community (MEA) currently being faced.

References

- Ahimsa, Shri Heddy, Putra (2012) Fenomenologi Agama : Pendekatan Fenomenologi Untuk Memahami Agama *Jurnal Walisongo Volume 20 Nomor 2*.
- Ar, Murniati (2009) Strategi Kepala Sekolah dalam Pemberdayaan Sekolah Menengah Kejuruan *Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan, Jilid 16, Nomor 2, Juni 2009.I*
- Assauri, Sofjan. (2013). *Strategic Management*. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada
- Fiandi, A., & Ilmi, D. (2022). Perkembangan Lembaga Pendidikan Islam Kontemporer. *An-Nidzam: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Dan Studi Islam*, 9(2), 206–218. <https://ejournal.iainu-kebumen.ac.id/index.php/An-Nidzam/article/view/999>
- Fiandi, A., & Sesmiarni, Z. (2023). Implementasi Standar Mutu Dan Sasaran Mutu Pada Lembaga Pendidikan. *EduTeach: Jurnal Edukasi Dan Teknologi Pembelajaran*, 4(1), 34–40. <https://doi.org/10.37859/eduteach.v4i1.4431>
- Mulyasa, E (2004), *Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah* Bandung, Remaja Rosda Karya.
- Mulayasa, E (2009), *Menjadi Kepala Sekolah Profesional*, Bandung, Remaja Rosda Karya.
- Rohiat (2008), *Kecerdasan Emosional Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah*, Bandung, Refika Aditama.
- Rohiat (2010) *Manajemen Sekolah*, Bandung, Refika Aditama.
- Rosyadi, Yogi Irfan, Pardjono (2015) Peran Kepala Sekolah Sebagai Manejer Dalam Meningkatkan Mutu Pendidikan di SMP 1 Cilawu Garut *Jurnal Akuntabilitas Manajemen Pendidikan Vol.3 No. 1 April 2015*.
- Sudradjat, Hari (2005) *Manajemen Peningkatan Mutu Berbasis Sekolah*, Bandung, Cipta Lekas Grafika
- Sukmadinata, Nana Syodih, Jami'at, Ayi Novi & Ahman (2010) *Pengendalian Mutu Pendidikan Sekolah Menengah* Bandung, Refika Aditama.
- Syukriah, Ana & Hamdani, Imam (2013) Peningkatan Eksistensi UMKM Melalui Comparative Advantage dalam Rangka Menghadapi MEA 2015 Di Temanggung *Economic Development Analysis Journal 2*.
- Tyas, Ari Anggaraini Winadi Prasetyoning, Safitri, Vita Intan (2014) Penguatan Sektor UMKM Sebagai Strategi Menghadapi MEA 2015 *Jurnal Ekonomi Vol. 5 No. 1*.
- Widodo, Heri (2015) Potret Pendidikan di Indonesia dan Kesiapannya dalam Menghadapi Masyarakat Ekonomi ASEAN (MEA) *Jurnal Cendikia Vol. 13 No.2 Juli – Desember 2015*
- Zainun (2001), *Manajemen Sumber Daya Strategik*, PT. Ghalia Cet. Ketiga.